

Analyst Administrator
Date Wednesday, June 1, 2022 2:02 PM

Sample Name	Description	Quality Checks
CAS-139_1	Sample 031 By Administrator Date Wednesday, June 01 2022	The Quality Checks do not report any warnings for the sample.